

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP), WP3 - FAIRyMAGs - Optimising Metagenomics Assembled Genomes building: workflow finalisation, training material development, real data evaluation and resource allocation tool creation

D3.3 Tutorial hosted on the Galaxy Training Network and visible on ELIXIR' TeSS

Tier: Science

Priority Area: Biodiversity, Food Security and Pathogens (BFSP)

Executive Summary

This deliverable covers the development of training materials supporting the Metagenome-Assembled Genomes (MAGs) generation workflows created by the FAIRyMAGs project.

To achieve this, a complete **learning pathway and a comprehensive tutorial** were developed and published in the [Galaxy Training Network \(GTN\)](#), guiding trainees step-by-step through all tasks required to generate MAGs. The learning pathway links in a comprehensive way different hands-on tutorials that cover in depth essential steps, from quality control and read preprocessing to assembly, binning, refinement, and annotation of MAGs. The tutorials used in the learning pathway correspond to both updated and expanded versions of existing GTN training materials, as well as newly developed content.

The newly created end-to-end tutorial guides learners through all steps of MAG generation by running the generated workflows (instead of individual tools as in the learning pathway) on an example dataset selected from a bee metagenome study (EBI ID: [PRJNA977416](#)) that was also used as a use case for this project. This enables learners to apply their knowledge to real-world datasets and supports scalability to large MAG projects.

All training materials are fully integrated into the GTN framework, and each tutorial is also available through ELIXIR's TeSS platform.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

GTN	Galaxy Training Network
MAG	Metagenome-Assembled Genomes
IWC	Intergalactic Workflow Commission

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A dedicated Metagenome-Assembled Genomes (MAGs) generation and annotation learning pathway

The GTN framework allows to establish topic specific [learning pathways](#). This pathway guides trainees step-by-step via modules, through a complex topic, allowing them to familiarize themselves and learn in-depth about the different steps. For the dedicated [Metagenome-Assembled Genomes \(MAGs\) generation and annotation learning pathway](#), the modules and materials were selected as follows:

Module	Tutorials
Module 0: Introduction to Galaxy – Navigating the Platform and Performing Your First Analysis	A short introduction to Galaxy Galaxy Basics for genomics
Module 1: Quality Control – Ensuring High-Quality Metagenomic Data	Quality Control
Module 2: Contamination and Host Reads Removal – Purifying Your Metagenomic Dataset	Remove contamination and host reads
Module 3: Assembly – Reconstructing and Assessing Contigs from Metagenomic Reads	Assembly of metagenomic sequencing data
Module 4: Binning – From Contigs to Refined Microbial Genomes	Binning of metagenomic sequencing data
<i>Hidden until the tutorial is online</i> Module 5: Taxonomic Assignment of MAGs – Identifying and Classifying Microbial Genomes	Tutorial still in development
Module 6: Functional Annotation of MAGs – Applying Genomic Approaches to Metagenome-Assembled Genomes	Bacterial Genome Annotation Identification of AMR genes in an assembled bacterial genome

To support this learning pathway, two tutorials ([Assembly of metagenomic sequencing data](#) and [Binning of metagenomic sequencing data](#)) were significantly updated to include all tools and analyses used in the generated MAGs workflows. The assembly tutorial was

thus updated to include more explanations on co-assembly and quality assessment, and to improve the text overall.

For the binning tutorial, a “Choose Your Own” training logic was included to allow the learner to bin contigs with any of 5 different bidders. In addition, it now covers bin-refinement, dereplication, and calculation of abundance information for binning. These major changes required a full update of the associated workflows as well as test data.

The tutorial [Remove contamination and host reads](#) for module 2 was newly developed, guiding how to remove host or contamination reads from metagenomic samples.

The tutorial *Taxonomic Assignment of MAGs* for module 5 is currently in development and should be ready in the next weeks to complete the learning pathway.

An end-to-end Metagenome-Assembled Genomes (MAGs) generation and annotation tutorial

While the learning pathway goes into detail about all steps required for MAGs generation, advanced users might be more interested in learning how to generate MAGs for their own projects. For those users, a [full end-to-end training was developed](#), which executes all workflows for MAGs generation and annotation instead of running individual steps. This tutorial can be used as a guide to execute the workflows on the user's own data. It explains how users can perform quality control, remove host contamination, and run the main MAGs workflow to obtain quality-controlled, taxonomically and functionally annotated MAGs. For that, 3 new workflows have been added to IWC and WorkflowHub: [Short read quality control](#), [Host removal short reads](#), [Host removal long reads](#).

The tutorial and workflows are illustrated by two samples from the bee microbiome, enabling learners to see how workflow outputs can be interpreted in a real-world context. Since processing large datasets can take a significant amount of time, pre-computed Galaxy histories are provided, allowing learners to explore results immediately without waiting for workflow execution to complete.

Once the version of the workflow for long-reads currently in development is ready, the tutorial will be extended to document it using a “Choose Your Own” training logic.

Outcomes and expected impact

This deliverable is fully aligned with the Capacity Building objectives defined in the project plan. While the developed Galaxy workflows already provide FAIR and accessible tools for generating MAGs, the accompanying training ensures that scientists at any experience level can understand both the technical and biological principles behind them. This empowers scientists to apply the workflows to their own data confidently

and effectively. Over time, well-trained scientists will be able not only to execute the workflows but also to adapt, optimize, and extend them with new methods and tools, actively contributing to their continued improvement and community-driven evolution.

Dissemination Plans

All tutorials, either in the learning pathway or the end-to-end tutorial, are publicly available on the Galaxy Training Network (GTN) and ELIXIR TeSS. One training still in development will be published upon completion.

The newly developed workflows are published in Intergalactic Workflow Commission (IWC) and WorkflowHub:

- [Short read quality control](#)
- [Host removal short reads](#)
- [Host removal long reads](#)

The end-to-end tutorial as well as the tutorial in the learning pathway will be recorded (including subtitles) to offer a MAGs building and annotation track in the Galaxy Training Academy, a one-week massive online training event that will happen in May 2026.

The learning pathway, end-to-end tutorial, and published workflows will be announced via a Galaxy blog post.